

Spectrophotometric Studies on Complexes of Vanadium (V) with Some N-Arylhydroxamic Acids

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Job's method of continuous variations as well as molar ratio method, as applied to two phase systems, have been used in order to establish the stoichiometry of vanadium(V)-N-arylhydroxamates extracted from 2-8N hydrochloric acid solutions. The metal to ligand ratio is found to be 1 : 2 in all the instances and the stability constants are of the order of 10^8 to 10^9 . The wavelength of maximum absorption and molar absorptivity for each complex is also given.

N-Arylhydroxamic acids are some of the most interesting organic reagents reported in recent times; they are claimed to be the most selective and sensitive reagents used so far for the colorimetric determination of vanadium¹⁻³. During the last two decades, numerous publications have appeared primarily on their varied analytical applications⁴⁻⁸. Relatively few studies have been reported on the metal complexes of hydroxamic acids, e.g., composition, stability, structure etc. Some attempt has been made in the direction of establishing the composition of vanadium(V) complexes of N-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid (PBHA)^{3,9} and N-o-tolylbenzohydroxamic acid¹⁰. Priyadarshini and Tandon⁹ have studied many N-acyl-substituted N-phenyl hydroxylamine derivatives to obtain more information on the factors influencing the selectivity and sensitivity of their reactions with metal ions. Similar investigations on several other substituted phenyl-hydroxyl-amines have been carried out by Ryan *et al.*^{11,12} to study the effect of change in the nature of the acyl group on their usefulness as analytical reagents. Very recently, Tandon and Bhattacharya have reported the absorption spectra and spectral characteristics of some vanadium(V)-N-arylhydroxamates¹³. No systematic effort seems to have been made, however, to throw light on the stoichiometry and stability of vanadium(V) chelates of the hydroxamic acids.

The present study has been conducted to establish spectrophotometrically the empirical composition of the vanadium(V) complexes of seven N-arylhydroxamic acids by Job's method of continuous variations as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper¹⁴ as well as molar ratio method¹⁵. Furthermore, the stability constants of all these chelates have been computed from their respective absorption data.

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus : A Unicam SP 500 quartz spectrophotometer, with two matched 10 mm Corex cells, was used for all photometric measurements.

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Reagents : Hydroxamic acids : N-Arylhydroxamic acids (Table 1) were either available as gifts from the co-workers of this laboratory or were prepared by the method of Priyadarshini and Tandon¹⁶. These were recrystallised, before use, from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether and were dried in vacuum over P₂O₅. The final purity of these compounds was established by m.p. elemental analyses, U.V. and I.R. spectra.

TABLE I
Description of N-Arylhydroxamic Acids

Compound Number	Hydroxyamic acid	General Formula :		Melting point °C	
		R ₁	R ₂	Found	Reported
I	N-Phenyl-(n)-butyro-	C ₆ H ₅ -	CH ₃ -(CH ₂) ₂ -	80	81 (16)
II	N-Phenylcapro-	C ₆ H ₅ -	CH ₃ -(CH ₂) ₄ -	65	64.5 (19)
III	N-p-Tolylcapri-	p-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃ -(CH ₂) ₈ -	84	85 (19)
IV	N-p-Tolylmyristo-	p-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃ -(CH ₂) ₁₂ -	80	79 (19)
V	N-Phenyl-2-furo-	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₄ H ₃ O-	135	134 (11)
VI	N-Phenylbenzo-	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	121	121 (20)
VII	N-Phenylcinnamo-	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₆ H ₅ -CH = CH-	161	162 (20)

Ammonium metavanadate : A stock solution was prepared by dissolving analytical grade ammonium metavanadate in glass-distilled water. Vanadium content of the solution was determined volumetrically using potassium permanganate solution¹⁷.

Ethyl alcohol-free chloroform : Ethyl alcohol was removed by washing the commercial chloroform five or six times with about half its volume of water and drying over fused calcium chloride. It was distilled and stored in a cool place in amber bottle.

For establishing the composition of complexes in solution a large number of studies were carried out by varying the concentrations of vanadium, hydroxamic acids, and hydrochloric acid and making absorption measurements at different wave lengths. Representative data for only a few studies are given in the form of graphs (Figs. 1 and 2). The adherence to Beer's law was always tested before making any absorption studies. Optical density-concentration graphs were plotted, they showed that the coloured solutions obey Beer's law over the concentration ranges used here.

Vanadium(V) reaction : Chloroform solutions of these acids react with V(V) solutions and yield chloroform extracts whose colours depend on the acid concentration of the aqueous phase. If the aqueous solution contains more than 2N HCl, violet extracts are always obtained, whereas if the HCl concentration is less than 0.1N (pH 1 to 6) mahogany red extracts are obtained. However, if the aqueous phase contains 0.1 to 2N HCl then the colour of the extracts is amethyst. The absorption spectra of vanadium(V)-PBHA coloured systems at different concentration of HCl in aqueous phase have been described earlier². In the

case of all reagents, under study, the effect of certain variables, such as acidity, time, volume of aqueous phase, ionic strength, and temperature on the colour development was found to be almost the same as reported in the above said system. For maximum colour development the concentration of hydrochloric acid in the aqueous phase should be approximately between 3 and 5*N*; most of our measurements were made at an acidity of about 4*N*, unless stated otherwise. It may be noted that the hydrochloric acid concentration here should not be higher than about 5*N*, since reduction of VO_2^+ to VO^{2+} by chloride ion occurs to an increasing extent with increase in the acid concentration⁹ and only vanadium(V) gives the desired violet complex with hydroxamic acid. Optical density measurements revealed, that all these chloroform extracts mostly show a broad absorption band; the sides of the band being symmetrical. The wavelength of maximum absorption, λ_{max} , lies in the region of 510–540 nm. This evidently suggests that only one complex is formed in solution¹⁴.

Stoichiometry of the complexes : The absorption due to mixtures of equimolar solutions of reagent and vanadate was measured in order to determine the metal to ligand ratio by Job's method. The procedure for a typical study was as follows :

Procedure : In a 100-ml dry separatory funnel was taken X ml of $1.8 \times 10^{-4}M$ vanadate solution, (10-X) ml of water, 5 ml of conc. HCl (sp. gr. 1.18), X ml of chloroform, and (10-X) ml of $1.8 \times 10^{-4}M$ reagent solution. The violet complex was extracted into chloroform and its absorbance measured.

For the molar ratio method, the procedure for a typical study was as follows :

In a 100-ml dry separatory funnel was taken 10 ml of $1.33 \times 10^{-4}M$ vanadate solution, 5 ml conc. HCl, Y ml reagent solution, and (10-Y) ml of chloroform. The ratio of V(V) to reagent was varied, with the former held constant, from 1 : 0.05, 1 : 2... to 1 : 30.

FIGURE - I

In both the above studies, the total volumes of aqueous and organic phases were always 15 ml and 10 ml respectively. Final volume was made upto 25 ml with chloroform in each case. The optical densities of these coloured extracts were measured at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ and at four wavelengths (510, 520, 530 and 540 nm) near the absorption band against chloroform as blank. Since the reagent solution in chloroform has no absorption at these wavelengths, the optical densities were plotted as such against the concentrations. All the Job's curves show sharp peaks at a molar ratio of 1 : 2 of metal : ligand. Plots for molar ratio method, however, show no such sharp breaks. Fig. 1 gives some typical curves.

Stability constant of the complexes : It was thought of interest to determine the stability constants of the complexes of vanadium(V) with all the hydroxamic acids. These were evaluated from a study of the absorptions obtained by molar ratio method (Fig. 2). The degree of dissociation, α , is given by the equation

$$\alpha = \frac{Em - Es}{Em}$$

where Em is the absorbance of the complex when excess of the reagent is present and Es is the absorbance of the complex at equivalent point. Hence, in the reaction $ML_2 \rightleftharpoons M^{+2} + 2L^{-}$ the stability constant K of the complex can be calculated from the following equation given by Harvey and Manning¹⁸.

$$K = \frac{(1-\alpha)}{4\alpha^3 C^2}$$

Here α and C denote the degree of dissociation and the total concentration of the complex in moles per liter assuming no dissociation respectively. Results obtained on the basis of these equations are given in Table 2. The free energy of formation ΔG° for each chelate, calculated according to Van't Hoff isotherm $\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K$ is also compiled in Table 2.

DISCUSSION

All the hydroxamic acids studied here give a deep violet complex with vanadate ions in strongly acidic solutions which seems to be of a very definite stoichiometry. An increase in acidity beyond 8N HCl destroys this complex. These coloured chelates are formed instantaneously and the stability of the systems is adequate for any analytical application. These violet complexes can be easily extracted from the aqueous phase with several organic solvents. Chloroform is found to be the most suitable extractant because : (i) the reagent is more freely soluble in it than in other solvents, (ii) quantitative extraction of the violet complex from the aqueous phase is readily accomplished; and (iii) the reagent solution has no absorption at the wavelength region of interest and hence optical density readings can be directly plotted without making any allowance for the self absorption of the reagent solution.

Table 2 clearly shows that the nature of the group attached to the carbonyl group has a marked effect on the spectral characteristics of the violet extracts. When an alkyl group is replaced by an aryl group here, the absorption band shifts to longer wavelengths and

TABLE 2

*Spectral Characteristics and Stability Constants of Vanadium(V)-N-Arylhydroxamates*Acidity of the Aqueous Phase : $\sim 4N$ (HCl) Temperature : $25 \pm 1^\circ$

Compound number	Colour of chloroform extract	Wavelength of maximum absorption (nm)	Molar absorptivity at λ_{\max}^* (lt./mole cm)	K ($\times 10^6$)	ΔG° (K.cal/mole)
I	RV	510	4445	51.2	-13.25
II	RV	500	4611	3.5	-11.66
III	RV	510	4167	15.8	-12.55
IV	RV	510	4522	30.6	-12.94
V	V	530	5167	7.4	-12.10
VI	V	530	4700	4.3	-11.79
		(530) ³	(4650) ¹³		
VII	BV	536	6379	8.2	-12.16
		(540) ¹³	(6300) ¹³		

(), Reported values. V, Violet. BV, Bluish violet. RV, Reddish violet.

* Mean of atleast 3 determinations and the values are believed to be within ± 50 lt./mole cm. These were measured at the corresponding λ_{\max} and are expressed in terms of vanadium.

the molar absorptivity also increases. The intensity, as exemplified by molar absorptivity, is naturally dependent on the nature of the attached groupings. The molar absorptivity increases with an increase in the extent of π system. As is expected, compound number V and VI possess a higher value as compared to compound number I to IV. This intensity is further enhanced by the introduction of side chain double bonds in conjugation with the $-C=O$ group, as seen in the case of compound number VII. It appears therefore that this class of compounds will prove more sensitive and/or selective in their colour reactions with metal ions. No significant change in the sensitivity for vanadium(V) colour reaction is found to take place when a more bulky group replaces the less one. Similarly the compound having a heterocyclic group in the R_2 position (V) shows no better improvement over the one possessing a phenyl or other aryl grouping (VI or VII).

An examination of Job's curves (plots shown in Fig. 1 for compound Nos I to VI) shows that in each of these complexes the metal to ligand ratio is 2 molecules of hydroxamic acid for one atom of vanadium. Similar conclusions have been drawn by Ryan³ and Priyadarshini⁹ in their studies with PBHA and by Majumdar and Das¹⁰ in their studies with *N*-*o*-tolylbenzohydroxamic acid. Further, the Job's curves obtained at different acidities, i.e., from 2-8*N* in HCl and at different wavelengths conclusively indicate that only one complex species is present in these acidic solutions. Likewise, studies made with different equimolar solutions of the reagents and vanadate ions also point to the above observation.

Studies on molar ratio method (plots shown in Fig. 2 for compound Nos. III to V only) reveal that there are no sharp breaks in the plots. The continuous curves become parallel to molar ratio axis when an excess of the hydroxamic acid is added. Results obtained by extrapolation of these plots are rather uncertain, although in a few instances, molar ratio close to 2 : 1 :: ligand : vanadate is observed.

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